

The impact of film and theater culture on the development of Chinese industry

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Abstract

With the global economic integration and the improvement of people's living standards, the impact of film culture on the tourism industry has become increasingly significant. This paper analyzes the role of film culture in promoting the tourism industry through multiple dimensions such as location selection, plot influence, celebrity effect and film type, and explores multiple global cases, such as the promotion of New Zealand tourism by "The Lord of the Rings" and its continued impact, and the role of the construction of Qingdao Oriental Movie Metropolis in China in promoting local economic development. Research shows that film culture can not only stimulate tourists' travel motivation, but also enhance the image of tourist destinations, achieve advertising effects, and promote the common development of the tourism industry chain. However, compared with the relatively mature film tourism system abroad, the development of Chinese film tourism is still in its early stages, with problems such as over-reliance on star effects, lack of systematic planning and cultural connotation mining.

In order to promote the sustainable development of Chinese film tourism, this paper proposes a series of countermeasures, including: establishing experiential tourism projects, using new media for publicity, seizing the opportunity for film tourism publicity, enhancing cultural connotations and strengthening government supervision. The research results provide theoretical reference and practical guidance for the deep integration of Chinese film and tourism industries.

Full Text Article

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Keywords: film culture, tourism industry, film and television tourism, economic development, sustainable development

Introduction

In the 21st century, the global economy has been integrated, and the economy has ushered in a peaceful and stable rapid development. Movies and tourism are the two most popular necessities of life for the people. With the improvement of people's living standards, most people like to go to the cinema and travel at home and abroad in their rest time. Before the impact of the covid-19, in China, in addition to traveling to some famous scenic spots, more and more young people like to follow their favorite movie shooting locations for a walk, such as Zhejiang Hengdian International Film and Television City, not only every year Hundreds of film and television dramas are filmed here, and many people will come to the filming location to travel and have the opportunity to get close to the actors. I have personally experienced it many times, and I will have many people watching while filming, which has a direct impact on the growth of the local economy.

Tourists believe they "must" visit multiple locations from the 1953 movie "Roman Holiday" in order to be considered to have been to Rome. They "imitation" Gregory Peck and Audrey Hepburn as they "ate ice cream on the Spanish Steps, rode a four-wheel carriage in the Colosseum, and "made a wish" at the Trevi Fountain, remembering this unforgettable moment; this is another opportunity for New Zealand's tourism industry to grow..(Leotta, Alfio.2011))(Carl, Daniela,2007)

Many years ago, my hometown Qingdao, China, now has China's industrial film and television base - Oriental Movie Metropolis. However, before building the investment base, investors invited Hollywood and superstars from all over the world, such as Leonardo DiCaprio, Nicole Kidman, Catherine Zeta-Jones, Zhang Ziyi, Jet Li, etc., their arrival also made Qingdao popular. In those days, the city of Qingdao was known to the world The arrival of people has also brought direct growth to Qingdao's tourism economy. However, the Oriental Movie Metropolis project has been in operation for many years, attracting many Hollywood films to come to shoot, and many Chinese and international cooperation films are in This shooting, Qingdao's tourism is also directly affected by the rising tide.

Film and television dramas are the natural carriers of tourism goods, from the United States to the success of Universal Studios and Disneyland, which are movie derivatives in many areas of the world, including China. The tourist sites, hotels for tourists, and other forms of According to the requirements, the majority of film and television works will be filmed in locations that have viewing value and meet the needs of the plot. The displayability and commercial value of local delicacies, even transportation and souvenirs, make the tourism industry a "golden master" actively sought by the film and television industry. As a result, travel-related products are utilized as the background for tourist marketing in movies and on television, which subtly draw viewers' attention.

In tourist sites that were inspired by film and television, a recent phenomena is known as "film and television product-induced tourism." Movie Beach (Thailand), Tomb Raider (Cambodia), Trap (Malaysia), The Lord of the Rings Trilogy (New Zealand), The Harry Potter Trilogy (UK), etc. are a few examples. This place has been mostly transformed into a well-liked tourist destination. However, tourist-oriented film offerings can often be erratic. Any film or television project's success cannot be assured, and inviting someone to visit can have complicated results. As a result, six aspects of cinema goods will be examined in this

article: setting, storyline, celebrity, film kind, and film festival. This study can aid in a better understanding of the context of film goods to promote tourism by highlighting certain film product characteristics. (Abd Rahman,2019)

As a result, the mutual advantage of the film and tourism sectors has led to their mutual influence, which has also evolved into an unavoidable trend in the growth of the film and tourism industries both domestically and internationally.(Kork, Yuri.2001)

Statement of Problems

Tourism New Zealand sent the well-known statistical surveying company NFO to conduct a Lord of the Rings market assessment in 2003. According to this survey, the majority of tourists and potential travelers have seen "The Lord of the Rings" movie, and up to 95% of them are Interviewers typically showed awareness of New Zealand's role as the film's shooting location. Nevertheless, 65% of potential tourists claimed that The Lord of the Rings and its associated showcasing had really made them want to visit to New Zealand, despite the film's massive success in the global film industry and its overall reported boost to New Zealand's travel economy. However, only 0.3% of tourists who actually went to New Zealand acknowledged that the movie was the main reason they went, while another 9% claimed that the movie was simply one of their travel inspirations. The enormous gap in the numbers indicates that even in the artistic creation "Master of the Rings," after the extraordinary development of the film and television has been sorted, the excess Litong who can directly contribute to the travel industry will be severely weakened. However, the more notable effect is the enormous scope.(Carl, Daniela,2007)

An in-depth examination of "The Lord of the Rings" movie's successful promotion to New Zealand's tourism sector reveals that the country's support for the movie extends beyond trade, taxation, and diplomacy; the government even named a representative as the "Lord of the Rings Minister" to be in charge of promoting travel, making investments, and setting up scenes for the movie. Additionally, it actively court visitors by hosting sizable conferences and exhibitions through a variety of brands and PR initiatives. Former New Zealand Prime Minister Helen Clark, flew to the United States to record 25 TV and radio shows for "Lord of the Rings Week", which can be regarded to have put forth all of their energy. In an effort to match the audience's "empathy" psychology, the filming location of Kaitoke Regional Park (Kaitoke Regional Park) was directly renamed the Rivendell in the play (Rivendell, where the elves are located). The brochures' inner pages detail the name of the movie scene (with photos) and the name of the location, allowing tourists to explore the "Middle-earth" in the movie according to the map. The New Zealand government's efforts have not gone in vain. Following "The Lord of the Rings" enormous popularity, New Zealand has been able to entice Hollywood productions like "The Chronicles of Narnia" and "The Last Samurai" to film there and use the money made from film and television tourists to make investments in the country. projects aiming to expand the film and television tourist sector sustainably.(Tzanelli, Rodanthi,2004)

Due to the late start of China's tourism and film and television industry, the promotion of tourism culture and film tourism has only been used in recent years. Therefore, compared

with foreign countries, China's research in this area is somewhat limited. In particular, there is a lack of definitions and definitions of some basic concepts, and more discussions are carried out from the perspective of film and television cities. Although there are many literatures and studies on tourism, in general, the research on the intersection of "film and television" and "tourism" in China is still in its infancy and has not formed a system. More is to rely on the star effect to attract tourists, but this is not a healthy development law of the tourism industry, it is very short-lived. Compared with foreign comprehensive research on film and television tourism, Chinese research mainly focuses on short-term development. From 1994 to 2001, the conceptual definitions of "film and television city" and "film and television tourism", or the simple accumulation of foreign research, lacked case or quantitative empirical research, and most of them were theoretical descriptions of the current situation and countermeasures. With the vigorous development of my country's tourism and film and television industry, from 2002 to 2008, Chinese scholars began to increase the number of case studies on film and television tourism, but most of them analyzed the development strategy and impact of film and television tourism from the economic level. The placement type and effect of advertisements, etc., as well as some existing problems. However, there is not much analysis on the impact and function of film and television tourism from the cultural level, and the content is not systematic and lacks depth. There is no work in this area.

The question is why the development of film tourism in China cannot be compared with that of foreign countries, and the development has encountered difficulties?

Research Methodology

Because we hope to have a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of film and television culture on the development of the tourism industry, rather than just draw targeted conclusions about a certain place or a certain film and television work, we did not use the commonly used field interviews and questionnaires for a certain case. Methods. The main research method I take is the literature method, that is, on the basis of a large amount of research on domestic and foreign related materials, including various documents, books and online news, I try to analyze and summarize the relevant elements of the theme, and supplement it with various cases. Explain, clarify the reasons for the occurrence of various situations, and aim to obtain a regular understanding.

Research Objective

1. Establish an experiential tourism project

Since the establishment of Disneyland, film and television tourism products have been developed for more than 50 years, which is more successful than that of foreign countries.

The domestic experience tourism for film and television tourism, which consists of tours of production locations and film and television bases, is still in its early stages for items like "Universal Studios" and "Harry Potter Theme Park". The classic "watching the lively" tourist experience is no longer sufficient to quench people's ardour for cinema and television tourism with the onset of the era of experiential consumption. To provide visitors the chance to

actively participate in and experience the reality of film and television, it is essential to make the most of gorgeous locations and film and television resources.

2. Promotion through new media

New media provides people based on shared interests or allows them to express their unique personalities. Traditional information publishers and audiences are now both information providers and can connect with one other quickly. platforms for communication, including social networking sites, Facebook, and others. One by one, virtual groups are created that do not know one another yet are similar. As a result, the recommendation or interest of a particular community member in a tourist site in the movie or television program will spread quickly from point to point to the entire community. Rapidity has become a propaganda position and natural carrier for "unexpected encounter" of film and television tourism. Secondly, the "grassroots" nature of online social media or self-media also makes it easier for communicators to establish trust and persuasion through an equal and cordial relationship, thereby improving the communication efficiency of film and television tourism marketing and the effectiveness of word-of-mouth marketing. (Lengkeek, J. G, 2001)

3. Grasp a good opportunity for film tourism promotion

The promotion of film and television tourism is limited by the film and television shooting cycle. Travelers need to take into account the "golden time" of tourism products and film and television release, so as to match the tourist destination with the film and television scene, so as to better show the unique charm of film and television tourism.

Additionally, both before and after the release of the film and television works, the tourist destination should conduct pertinent publicity activities in advance, such as updating the tourist destination's hardware equipment and service facilities or developing a more consistent image in the play, to ensure that people who "come here" Tourists have a greater intimacy, as if they are incarnated as the hero and heroine in the play, and will not feel a gap that is remote from the play. Film and television tourism products that exceed viewer expectations may bring negative impacts and a bad reputation, even though it is generally recognized that film and television dramas as an artistic medium cannot be completely equivalent to reality. (Chen, Huan, 2021)

4. Enhance the cultural connotation of film and television tourism

The first step in enhancing the cultural connotation of cinema and television tourism is to create exceptional film and television works, making them a resource and a way to draw viewers. It is also essential to be skilled at identifying the cultural significance of tourist sites. Through the use of propaganda in films and television, many picturesque locations are artificially constructed. Due to the lack of historical and cultural implications, it can become popular quickly, but it is difficult to create a climate. On the other hand, there are some locations with distinctive landscape but no name that shine through the film and television foil.

5. Strengthen government supervision

It is hoped that the government can rationally allocate market resources by mobilizing and coordinating various social organizations and industries. Politics

The financial assistance, planning, and management of the film and television tourist sector by the government, along with cross-border and cross-border collaboration, would have a favorable effect on the film and television industry, tourism, and even the perception of the entire nation. Second, the development of cinema and television tourism is predicated on the quality of film and television dramas, which serve as the central carrier and soul of film and television culture. As a result, the government should implement pertinent measures, such as tax exemptions or reductions, the creation of funds, or a laxer stance on credit regulations, to provide incentives to the film and television tourist business.

Significant of research

It is vital to focus on and deliberately employ cinema and television attempts to push neighborhood the travel industry and financial turn of events since film culture plays a significant role in the advancement of traveler concerns. The influence of motion movies is also ephemeral. Instead of relying on the fleeting fame of film and TV, unique regular beauty or significant social allure, supporting superior grade and smart assistance levels, and successfully keeping up with and further developing the travel industry climate are the ways to really make tourists want to visit inside and out or even return to a location.

The send off of notable film and TV works has either determined the quick thriving of a grand spot, or further solidified the standing of the current notable the travel industry asset scene. Whether emotional or inadvertent, effective film and TV works will drive the advancement of nearby the travel industry. The advancement and effect of film and TV the travel industry on the travel industry are encapsulated in the accompanying viewpoints:

(1) Promoting the travel industry inspiration

By using light and shadow techniques, the film and media industries creatively depict the local culture or stunning natural view of the filming location, tie the story and the characters into the pleasant environment of the set, and put everything together to create an exciting or amicable ideal. This allows the audience to put themselves into the film and television. One of them is the opportunity to see the actual natural settings and images used in movies and television shows, which is the main source of inspiration for tourists who travel for movies and television shows.

(2) Establish a travel industry picture

Film and TV have the attributes of the mix of sound and picture, and the blend of sound and picture, which makes the recording area more lovely and alluring when seen through the film and TV. Simultaneously, the story content of the film and TV dramatization will likewise add a marvelous social tone to the recording area, imperceptibly reinforce individuals' feeling of magnificence in the shooting area, and lay out a decent vacationer picture of the recording area.

(3) Advertising impact

Prior to filming, the majority of TV and film projects were progressed. When dramatizations are broadcast on film or television, the channels and types of exposure are expanded, including media exposure, recording features, star impacts, etc. Meanwhile, new information about various locations keeps emerging, making them stand out to potential tourists, sparking their interest, and amplifying the effect of exposure to the travel industry.

(4) Encourage the cycle of normal improvement in the tourism sector

The development of the film and television travel industry has directly or indirectly influenced the improvement of various travel industry components and improved the chain's organization.

Consider the movie and TV city as an example. The presence of numerous movie teams will entice a large number of tourists to visit, increase ticket sales, and consequently promote the advancement of other travel industry components like lodging and food, traveler souvenirs, and tourist transportation. The production of film and television dramas has also influenced the growth of related businesses, such as the production of props, the supply of camera equipment, and so forth, framing the travel industry and film and television shooting as the primary bodies close to the film and television city., spanning a wide range of elements, including food, hotel, transportation, and shopping. The massive modern chain, which is beneficial for growing local business, is operating honestly and rationally to boost the target travel sector.

Conclusion

Similar to other research areas in tourism, this one began in the West, and foreign academics have The topic of combined research is "Movie-induced Tourism" or "Film-induced Tourism."Expand, this keyword highlights the interaction between film and television and tourism as well as a new type of tourism and tourism-related products.The study process with the theme of cinema and television tourism is brief in comparison to the successful outcomes that have been achieved in other domains of tourist research.And the majority of them lack a developed theoretical paradigm and are simply recaps of cases. however, the accumulated knowledge of academics from around the globe.The research's breadth and depth are being increased from many perspectives, making it more comprehensive.

When compared to study conducted in other nations, domestic research lagged behind, had fewer participants, and had more narrowly focused viewpoints. The majority of the early studies—film and television city and film and television base—directly addressed the combination of film and television and tourism. The straightforward claim of many academics that "film and television tourism originated from theme parks" is true. Better utilization of film and television resources ignores the autonomous function of film and television itself as a communication medium in encouraging tourism growth, beginning with the construction and development of such unique theme parks.

There hasn't been a monograph on this topic yet. The publications dispersed over different journals primarily appeared after 2005. The majority of them began by discussing the promotion of the film and television industry to the development of destination tourism in

film and television cities or location locations; or by sorting out the instances of film and television works driving the development of tourist destinations; and by offering recommendations for the government to promote local film and television tourism.

In the related researches in the past, "film and television tourism" was often studied as a whole, and the definition of "film and television tourism" was not very clear. After splitting the two keywords in "film and television tourism", focus on the process of impact occurrence (ie English "induced" in the concept of film-induced tourism), not the final result.

In order to build a model that can more completely reflect the impact of film and television on tourism, this paper splits "tourism" It is divided into two parts: "tourists" and "tourist destinations", and then respectively studies the influence of film and television on them, and considers the subject and object.

Self-motivation, emphasizing the way their responses can more fully complement the effects. This structure of simultaneously studying the influence of tourism subjects and objects is also a major innovation.

Another point is that this article is a comparative study of the development of foreign film tourism in China, highlighting the advantages and disadvantages.

Disadvantage: Although this article analyzes different influences at home and abroad, it lacks on-the-spot investigations, most of which are literature analysis, which cannot fully and objectively reflect the truth, and are also affected by sudden force majeure factors, such as the current covid-19.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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